

Discuss the links between the carbon cycle and climate change, and show how human interference in this cycle can accelerate or decelerate warming.

Changes in climate are a natural occurrence, however the concentrations of common greenhouse gases (GHGs), like methane and carbon dioxide, have never, in the 650,000 years that polar ice cores record, have been observed at current levels (Grace 2008). Furthermore, the IPCC (2021, p.676) states that the increase of such GHGs is ‘unequivocal[ly]’ due to human activity. The vast increase of GHGs in the atmosphere is an issue, and though methane is the more potent of the two, carbon dioxide’s atmospheric lifetime is nearly 10 times that of methane (Woodward, 2004, as cited in Grace, 2008). To understand why there are increased concentrations of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, one must understand its role in climactic change and the carbon budget.

The carbon budget is an understanding of where the Earth’s carbon dioxide is allocated at any given time; but it is calculated in different ways, though demonstrates the effects of human activity (IPCC 2021). The ‘remaining carbon budget’ refers to how much CO₂ can be emitted before an additional 1.5-2C of warming, since the industrial era, will occur (IPCC 2021). Likewise, “When the remaining carbon budget is combined with all past CO₂ emissions to date, a ‘total carbon budget’ [is made]” (IPCC 2021, p.777). See figure 1 for total carbon budget of years 2010-19.

Figure 1: “Global carbon budget (2010-19)” Source: IPCC, 2021, p.700

One feature of the carbon budget is the ability to clearly see transfer of CO₂ throughout the biosphere. One location of major transfer is between land and atmosphere. A major natural performer in this is photosynthesis and organic respiration. Photosynthesis draws carbon dioxide out of the atmosphere, as plants combine it and water with sunlight, to generate energy for themselves and oxygen as a byproduct. Organic respiration, on the other hand, performed by auto and heterotrophs alike, adds carbon dioxide back into the atmosphere. When in combination with wildfires, of natural and anthropogenic varieties, carbon output from the land is nearly equal to that of its’ input, see figure 1. This shows clear linkage between the carbon cycle and climate change, as carbon dioxide in the atmosphere absorbs infrared radiation, which increases the greenhouse effect, further warming the planet (Grace 2008). Although, humans decrease the carbon sequestration abilities of autotrophs like trees, through rapid deforestation. Often done with fire, this allows for the sequestered carbon in forests to be released, and the land to be wiped of carbon storage abilities. This affect can be seen on figure 1 under ‘total respiration and fire’, ‘gross photosynthesis’, and ‘net land-use change’, all anthropogenic effects are denoted by the pink colouration. Another place for carbon to be stored safely outside of the atmosphere is in the ground, see figure 1 ‘soil’,

‘vegetation’ and ‘permafrost’. In the form of deceased organic life or trapped gases, it is a container for vast amounts of carbon, and vaster amounts of energy. The burning of these stored fossil fuels, similar to forests, emits all their sequestered carbon back into the atmosphere. This acceleration of climate change by human activity can also be seen in figure 1, where fossil fuels made up 81-91% of anthropogenic carbon emissions, at 445 billion tons of CO₂ emitted from 2010-19 (IPCC 2021). It is ‘unequivocal’ that without human interference in the carbon cycle, via acceleration of its emittance, the climate would not be warmed to the extent seen today.

Human interference is not limited to land and atmosphere relations. Land to ocean and other water related processes also involve carbon, effect climate change, and have been impacted by humans. Soil, which stores organic matter and therefore carbon, can be transported by rivers which will redeposit the sediment along the riverbed or into the ocean, which buries the carbon. This reduces the possibility of soil disturbance to release the carbon into the atmosphere and increase GHG emissions. Humans, however, will often disturb soils through farming, construction and other land-use changes, which return the carbon to the atmosphere, see figure 1 ‘land-use change’, ‘exports from soils to rivers’, ‘rivers’ and ‘burial’. Wetlands are another natural biome of carbon sequestration. Raey *et al.* (2007, p.9) explains how, “the anoxic conditions prevailing in swamps and peatlands allow for efficient preservation of ... plant material”. The organic compounds of dead plants prove to hold their carbon, and therefore energy, and are formed in a relatively short time span. Despite this, they are created 100 times slower than the rate at which fossil fuels were being burned in 2007 (Raey *et al.*). Human interference in land uses increases the atmospheric CO₂ concentrations through land disruption due to land-use changes. This in turn warms the climate, with human activity as a clear accelerant.

Despite these human effects on climate, the ocean and atmosphere exchange CO₂ in an attempt to reach temperature equilibrium. Since vast ocean waters take longer to heat up under warmer temperatures, they can not only hold more heat, but more carbon dioxide as well. They take so much longer to heat up, in fact, that the IPCC (2021) predicts that the ocean may transition from carbon sink to source, and begin emitting carbon dioxide in the early parts of next century. The atmosphere-ocean gas exchange is an important process; however, it only involves the very top layer of the ocean. Ocean circulation allows for warmer, carbon rich waters to be replaced by cooler, more CO₂ soluble polar waters, see figure 1 ‘intermediate and deep-sea’ (Raey *et al.* 2007). Unfortunately, the increase in

atmospheric temperatures from increased CO₂ concentrations means that the ocean on average is warmer (IPCC 2021). Not only this but circulation can be affected by prolonged warm periods which reduce the transport of cool water to replace the warm, and ocean carbon sequestration becomes less efficient (Raey *et al.* 2007). Additionally, prolonged warm periods will become more common as the greenhouse effect increases and natural process, like El Niño, increase in overall impact through temperature (Grace 2008). The low carbon solubility of warmer water also results in increased stratification, then affecting the nutrients available to phytoplankton, leading to repercussions on the entirety of the oceanic ecosystem (Raey *et al.* 2007). Oceanic organisms are majorly affected by increased anthropogenic dissolved CO₂ in oceans which cause acidification (IPCC 2021), an estimated 118 billion tons of CO₂ between 1800 and 1994 were deposited into the ocean (Raey *et al.* 2007, p.7). Carbon in the oceans is in the form of bicarbonate 90% of the time, and carbonate 8% (Raey *et al.* 2007), which under normal circumstance would not affect pH to the current extent, due to human activity (IPCC 2021). Decreasing pH and increasing acidification are most common in deep convection regions like the subpolar Atlantic and Southern Oceans, which drive the transportation of cooler waters to regulate ocean temperatures (IPCC 2021). With this process slowing or stopping cool water is unable to circulate to the surface, and the oceans' sequestration abilities are decreased. Anthropogenic effects of increased CO₂ concentration are changing the ocean physically in temperature and circulation, and chemically in pH and bicarbonate levels to further augment the climate.

Fortunately, despite our mistakes, there are still many ways humans are attempting, and succeeding, in decreasing carbon emissions. An easy way to do this is to remove carbon straight from the atmosphere via carbon capture, however, the amount deliberately removed by humans needs to exceed the amount produced by them (IPCC 2021). Not only this but some climate trends are 'locked-in', the IPCC (2021, p.p.774-5) explains that though global temperature would reduce in years, "other aspects of climate change would take decades (e.g., permafrost thawing) or centuries (e.g., acidification of the deep ocean) to reverse, and some, such as sea level rise, would take centuries to millennia". Not to mention carbon capture's negative side-effects on water systems, agriculture and biodiversity (IPCC 2021). Debatably an even easier way would be to stop carbon emissions for energy-use altogether. The Paris Climate Agreement had countries to set goals towards net-zero emissions, in attempt to stay below an additional 1.5-2Cs of warming. Renewable energies like wind, solar, hydroelectric, biomass, nuclear, and even tidal systems are being explored and engineered to

reduce both global and personal carbon emissions. Enhancing preexisting carbon sinks is also an option; protecting remaining forests and planting new ones, leaving soils undisturbed in agricultural practices, protecting peatlands, wetlands and swamps, even ocean fertilization has been proposed (Grace 2008, p.608). Grace (2008) also notes how deep-ocean phytoplankton lack micronutrients like iron, so when added, it enhances productivity of the ecosystem, leading to increased carbon sequestration from decaying biota and carbonate shells stratifying on the ocean floor. The oceans, atmosphere, and land will continue to exchange carbon, and attempt to reach equilibrium while cooling the climate through their own carbon sequestration tactics. So, despite anthropogenic carbon emissions accelerating climate change through the carbon cycle's natural links with climate, more advanced and informed decisions are being made to revert the climate to preindustrial levels.

Reference List

- Grace, J. (2008). *Learning Objectives*. [online] Essex: Pearson Education UK. Available at: https://www.pearsonhighered.com/assets/samplechapter/h/o/l/d/Holden_2e_C21_screen_optimize.pdf [Accessed 10 Feb. 2024].
- IPCC, (2021) Canadell, J.G., P.M.S. Monteiro, M.H. Costa, L. Cotrim da Cunha, P.M. Cox, A.V. Eliseev, S. Henson, M. Ishii, S. Jaccard, C. Koven, A. Lohila, P.K. Patra, S. Piao, J. Rogelj, S. Syampungani, S. Zaehle, and K. Zickfeld, 2021: Global Carbon and other Biogeochemical Cycles and Feedbacks. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 673–816, doi: [10.1017/9781009157896.007](https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896.007) [Accessed 10 Feb. 2024].
- Reay, D. (2007). *Greenhouse Gas Sinks*. [online] *Internet Archive*. Wallingford, Oxfordshire, UK ; Cambridge, MA : CABI. Available at: https://archive.org/details/isbn_9781845931896/page/6/mode/2up [Accessed 10 Feb. 2024].